

GC-MS ANALYSIS OF LEAF VOLATILE OIL FROM CALLISTEMON CITRINUS (CURTIS) SKEELS AND COMPARATIVE COMPOSITION STUDY OF GLOBAL VARIETIES: INSIGHTS FROM LITERATURE DATA

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ABSTRACT

Callistemon citrinus (Curtis) Skeels, a species belonging to the Myrtaceae family, is well-known for its fragrant essential oils, which have both therapeutic and industrial value. Among its various bioactive components, 1,8-cineole stands out due to its well-documented benefits in managing respiratory conditions. This research focuses on analyzing the chemical makeup of essential oil extracted from the leaves of *Callistemon citrinus* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The objective is to compare the chemical profile of the Roorkee (India) sample with those reported from other regions around the world. The study aims to assess how geographical variation affects the oil's composition and explore its implications for medicinal and commercial use. Fresh leaves of *Callistemon citrinus* were collected from the Roorkee region in India for the study. Essential oils were obtained through hydro distillation and subjected to GC-MS analysis to identify and quantify the

constituents. The analysis revealed the presence of 22 different volatile compounds. Published literature from various geographical locations was reviewed to facilitate comparative analysis. GC-MS profiling revealed that 1,8-cineole was the dominant compound, making up approximately 75.40% of the total oil content. Other key constituents included α -terpineol, terpinen-4-ol, α -pinene, β -pinene, P-Cymene, and limonene. Notably,

the 1,8-cineole concentration in the Roorkee sample was significantly higher than in oils extracted from most of the regions, suggesting potentially greater effectiveness for respiratory applications. This research offers a detailed overview of the chemical composition of *Callistemon citrinus* essential oil, with a particular focus on the notably high level of 1,8-cineole found in the samples collected from Roorkee. These findings suggest strong potential for its use in respiratory therapies, aromatherapy, and pharmaceutical formulations. The observed variation in oil composition across regions emphasizes the importance of considering geographical factors in essential oil standardization and commercialization.

KEYWORDS: *Callistemon spp*, Essential oil, GC-MS analysis, Comparison, 1,8-cineole.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *callistemon*, consisting of around thirty-four species of evergreen shrubs and small trees, is widely cultivated for both its ornamental appeal and essential oil production. Among these species, *Callistemon citrinus* stands out for its medicinal properties, which include anti-cough, anti-bronchitis, and insecticidal activities. Furthermore, various *callistemon* species have been shown to exhibit a range of other biological activities, such as antiphylococcal, nematocidal, larvicidal, pupicidal, antithrombotic, and antioxidant effects. The antimicrobial properties of their volatile oils have also been well-documented, making *callistemon* a subject of growing interest in the field of natural products and alternative medicine.^[1]

However, one of the significant challenges in utilizing *Callistemon* essential oils for therapeutic and industrial purposes is the variability in their chemical composition. The concentration of active compounds within the volatile oils can vary greatly depending on a range of environmental factors such as geographical location, climate, soil composition, altitude, and cultivation practices. For instance, plants grown in areas with distinct seasonal variations may produce oils with different compositions compared to those grown in more stable environments. This variation can influence the ratio of bioactive compounds in the oil, ultimately impacting the oil's therapeutic efficacy. As a result, the bioactivity of *Callistemon* oils may differ depending on the environmental conditions in which the plants are grown, making it essential to profile and compare these oils from diverse regions to fully understand their medicinal potential.^[2]

In this context, the present study focuses on analysing the essential oil composition of *C. citrinus* leaves collected from Roorkee, India, in January 2025. The goal is to compare these

findings with published data on other *callistemon* species from various global regions, highlighting differences and similarities in oil composition based on geographic origin. To carry out this comparative analysis, the study will utilize gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (gc-ms), a highly accurate and widely accepted method for identifying and quantifying the complex constituents of volatile plant oils.^[3]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Collection and Authentication: Fresh leaves of *Callistemon citrinus* were collected in January 2025 from the Puhana region near Roorkee, located in the state of Uttarakhand, India. The collection site lies at 29.87°N latitude and 77.88°E longitude, with an approximate elevation of 268 meters above sea level. A voucher specimen (Voucher No. M-C-P078) of the plant was prepared and deposited in the herbarium of the Faculty of Science, Motherhood University, Roorkee, Uttarakhand, for future reference. The plant was authenticated by Dr. Avadhesh Kumar Koshal, a qualified botanist, to ensure correct taxonomic identification.

Essential Oil Extraction

A total of 200 g of fresh *C. citrinus* leaves were processed for essential oil extraction. The leaves were subjected to hydrodistillation using a Clevenger-type apparatus for a period of three hours. During this process, the steam carried volatile compounds from the plant material, which were then condensed and separated from the distillate. The obtained essential oil was carefully collected, separated from the aqueous phase, and stored in airtight glass vials at 4 °C to prevent degradation and preserve its chemical integrity until further analysis.^[4] The yield of the essential oil was calculated relative to the weight of the fresh plant material and was found to be approximately 0.6% (w/w).

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS) Analysis

The chemical constituents of the essential oil were analyzed using a GCMS-TQ8040 system (Shimadzu) equipped with a mass-selective detector. The separation of components was performed on a capillary column (Rxi-5ms, 30 m × 0.25 mm, 0.25 µm film thickness). Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.50 ml min⁻¹, ensuring efficient resolution of volatile compounds.

The oven temperature program was set as follows

- Initial hold at 60°C for 10 minutes
- Gradual increase to 180 °C at 3 °C/min, held for 5 minutes

- Further increase to 280 °C at 5 °C/min, followed by another 5-minute hold

The injector temperature was maintained at 280 °C, and the sample was introduced using a split/splitless injector in split mode with a 10:1 ratio. A 1 µL aliquot of the essential oil, diluted in dichloromethane, was injected into the system.

Detection was performed using electron ionization (EI) at an energy of 70 electron volts (eV), which effectively ionized the compounds for spectral analysis. Data acquisition was carried out in full scan mode over a mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) range of 45 to 550. The identification of individual constituents was carried out by confirming their mass spectral fragmentation patterns against the standard mass spectral databases NIST05 mass spectral library. The percentage composition of each compound was calculated using the area normalization technique.^[5,6]

RESULTS

A total of 22 distinct chemical constituents were identified from the *Callistemon citrinus* leaf essential oil. These included a variety of terpenes, terpenoids, and aliphatic compounds. Details of the identified components, along with their retention times, similarity indices, and relative concentrations (expressed as area percentage), are summarized in Table 1. The GC-MS chromatogram representing the chemical profile of the leaf oil is provided in Figure 1. The GC-MS mass spectra of the major constituents of the essential oil, along with their chemical structures are present in Figure 2-6.

Table 1: Chemical constituents of *Callistemon citrinus* leaf oil from Roorkee (North India).

Peak No.	Retention Time	Compounds	Area %	Similarity Index
1	5.32	Bicyclo[3.1.0]hex-2-ene, 2-methyl-5-(1-methylethyl)-	0.09	94
2	5.51	Alpha-Pinene	3.74	96
3	6.68	Beta-Pinene	0.53	97
4	6.98	Beta-Myrcene	0.24	95
5	7.65	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-, 3-methylbutyl ester	0.11	97
6	8.06	P-Cymene	1.89	96
7	8.22	Limonene	5.65	96
8	8.34	1,8-cineole	75.40	97
9	9.13	Gamma-Terpinene	0.47	97
10	10.51	Linalool	0.75	97
11	13.32	Terpinen-4-ol	1.00	95

12	13.84	Alpha-Terpineol	7.95	96
13	15.81	Geraniol	0.25	96
14	16.34	5-methyl-5-nitro-2-(prop-1-en-1-yl)-1,3-dioxane	0.35	80
15	19.30	Eugenol	0.25	91
16	24.61	Dihydroquinone	0.24	80
17	25.31	6-isobutyryl-2,2,4,4-tetramethylcyclohexane-1,3,5-trione (Flavesone)	0.28	91
18	26.56	Spathulenol	0.13	95
19	26.73	Caryophyllene oxide	0.31	95
20	26.85	Globulol	0.13	94
21	27.89	2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-6-(3-methylbutanoyl)cyclohexane-1,3,5-trione (leptospermone)	0.11	82
22	28.01	2-naphthalenemethanol, 2,3,4,4a,5,6,7,8-octahydro-alpha, alpha,4a,8-tetramethyl-,(2R-(2, alpha,4a beta, 8 beta)- (+)Rosifoliol	0.13	88

The published literature data on the chemical components of essential oils from *Callistemon* species grown in various regions worldwide will be used for comparing with the presently studied oil obtained from leaf of *Callistemon citrinus* grown in Roorkee, India.

Fig. 1: GC-MS Chromatogram of leaf essential oil sample of *Callistemon citrinus* (Curtis) Skeels.

Peak Report TIC

Peak#	Name	R Time	Base m/z	Area	Area%	Height	Height%
1	Bicyclo[3.1.0]hex-2-ene, 2-methyl-5-(1-methylethyl)-	5.322	93.05	262656	0.09	132940	0.14
2	alpha-Pinene	5.515	93.05	10882729	3.74	5316627	5.68
3	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptane, 6,6-dimethyl-2-methylene-, (1S)-	6.686	93.05	1541527	0.53	718848	0.77
4	beta-Myrcene	6.983	93.05	702107	0.24	324868	0.35
5	Propanoic acid, 2-methyl-, 3-methylbutyl ester	7.655	70.05	310916	0.11	143971	0.15
6	p-Cymene	8.058	119.10	5490995	1.89	2130947	2.28
7	D-Limonene	8.219	68.05	16426606	5.65	4973667	5.31
8	Eucalyptol	8.343	81.05	219251128	74.40	67316118	71.51
9	gamma-Terpinene	9.130	93.05	1355368	0.47	574901	0.61
10	Linalool	10.511	71.05	2176021	0.75	860924	0.92
11	3-Cyclohexen-1-ol, 4-methyl-1-(1-methylethyl)-, (R)-	13.320	71.05	2917893	1.00	1110279	1.19
12	L-alpha-Terpineol	13.842	59.05	23121362	7.95	8008395	8.56
13	2,6-Octadien-1-ol, 3,7-dimethyl-, (Z)-	15.816	69.05	718680	0.25	255367	0.27
14	5-Methyl-5-nitro-2-(prop-1-en-1-yl)-1,3-dioxane	16.345	69.00	1020900	0.35	362204	0.39
15	Phenol, 2-methoxy-3-(2-propenyl)-	19.300	164.05	718937	0.25	204437	0.22
16	Durohydroquinone	24.610	166.05	699180	0.24	203442	0.22
17	6-Isobutyryl-2,2,4,4-tetramethylcyclohexane-1,3,5-trione	25.317	164.10	822770	0.28	248409	0.27
18	1H-Cycloprop[<i>e</i>]azulen-7-ol, decahydro-1,1,7-trimethyl-	26.566	119.05	386110	0.13	112365	0.12
19		26.729	79.05	902219	0.31	279073	0.30
20	(-)-Globulol	26.851	107.05	378191	0.13	110567	0.12
21	2,2,4,4-Tetramethyl-6-(3-methylbutanoyl)cyclohexane-1,3-dione	27.890	57.10	314047	0.11	100551	0.11
22	2-Naphthalenemethanol, 2,3,4,4a,5,6,7,8-octahydro-alpha, alpha, 4a,8-tetramethyl-, [2R-(1S,2S,4S,5S)]	28.007	59.05	389289	0.13	121684	0.13
				290787631	100.00	93610584	100.00

Figure 2: GC–MS mass spectrum of α -pinene ($C_{10}H_{16}$; MW: 136; CAS: 80-56-8) obtained from NIST17 library. The major fragment ion is observed at m/z 93, with additional characteristic peaks at m/z 41, 77, 105, and 136, confirming the identity of α -pinene. Retention index: 948.

Figure 3: GC–MS mass spectrum of D-limonene (C₁₀H₁₆; MW: 136; CAS: 5989-27-5) identified using the NIST17 library. The spectrum shows characteristic fragment ions at *m/z* 68, 93, 121, and 136, consistent with D-limonene. Retention index: 1018.

Figure 4. GC–MS mass spectrum of p-cymene (C₁₀H₁₄; MW: 134; CAS: 99-87-6) identified using the NIST17 library. Key fragment ions are detected at *m/z* 119, 91, and 134, supporting the identification of p-cymene. Retention index: 1042.

Figure 5. GC–MS mass spectrum of eucalyptol (1,8-cineole) (C₁₀H₁₈O; MW: 154; CAS: 470-82-6) identified using the NIST17 library. Prominent peaks appear at *m/z* 43, 81, 108, 139, and 154, confirming eucalyptol. Retention index: 1059.

Figure 6. GC–MS mass spectrum of L- α -terpineol (C₁₀H₁₈O; MW: 154; CAS: 10482-56-1) identified using the NIST17 library. Major fragment ions are observed at *m/z* 59, 93, 121, and 136, confirming the identity of L- α -terpineol. Retention index: 1143.

Table 2: Major volatile oil components of *Callistemon* species grown in various regions worldwide in comparison with oil obtained from Roorkee, Uttarakhand.

Origin		Major Components	Reference
Eastern Cape of South Africa <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (flowers)		α -Eudesmol (12.93%), Caryophyllene (11.89%), Bornyl-acetate (10.02%), 1,8-cineole (8.11%), Bicyclogermacrene (5.71%) and γ -Eudesmol (5.21%).	(7)
Eastern Cape of South Africa <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (leaf)		1,8-cineole (48.98%), α -Pinene (20.02%), α -Terpineol (8.10%), Isopinocarveol (5.75%) and Pinocarvone (2.81%).	(7)
Eastern Cape of South Africa <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (stems)		1,8-cineole (56.00%) and α -Pinene (31.03%).	(7)
Palampur, Himachal Pradesh Western Himalaya <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (flowers)		1,8-cineole (36.6%), α -Pinene (29.7%).	(8)
Palampur, Himachal Pradesh Western Himalaya <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (leaf)		1,8-cineole (9.8%) α -Pinene (32.3%), Limonene (13.1%), α -Terpineol (14.6%)	(8)
Khuzestan province in South-West of Iran (leaf) <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>		1,8-cineole (34.20%), α -Pinene (29.0%), α -Terpineol (16.70%), α -Phellandrene (9.0%).	(9)
Province of Gilan Iran	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (leaf)	1,8-cineole (67.60%), α -Pinene (9.40%), β -Pinene (4.70%)	(10)
	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (flowers)	α -Pinene (25.70%), 1,8-cineole (18.10%), β -Pinene (7.30%), Linalool (5.30%).	(10)
	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (stems)	1,8-cineole (41.30%), α -Pinene (19.10%), α -Terpineol (4.10%),	(10)
Saint-Gilles to La Saline France Reunion Island <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> (leaf)		1,8-cineole (68.0%), α -Pinene (12.80%), α -Terpineol (10.6%).	(11)
Dehradun, Lower(leaf) Region of Himalaya <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>		1,8-cineole (66.30%), α -Pinene (18.70%)	(3)
Province of KwaZulu-Natal South Africa (leaf) <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>		1,8-cineole (61.20%), α -Pinene (13.40%), β -Pinene (4.70%)	(12)
Province of KwaZulu-Natal South Africa (leaf) <i>Callistemon viminalis</i>		1,8-cineole (83.20%), α -Pinene (6.40%), β -Pinene (0.9%)	(12)

Lahore, Pakistan (leaf) <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>	1,8-cineole (44.6%), α -Terpineol (31.0%)	(13)
Lahore, Pakistan (flowers) <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>	1,8-cineole (18.3%), α -Terpineol (5.2%) α -Pinene (42.7%)	(13)
Eastern Cape of South Africa (leaf) <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>	1,8-cineole (26.43%), α -Pinene (12.39%), α -Terpineol (6.78%), Isopinocarveol (5.29%) and Pinocarvone (2.74%).	(14)
Roorkee (North India) <i>C. lanceolatus</i> leaf	1,8-cineole (75.4%), Terpinen-4-ol(1%)Alpha-Terpineol (7.95%)D-Limonene(5.65%) P-Cymene(1.89%)Alpha-Pinene(3.74%)	Present study
Alexandria-cairo Road Egypt (<i>C. comboynensis</i>) leaf	1,8-cineole (53.3%), Methyleugenol (9.2%), Eugenol (12.1%) Alpha Pinene (8.3%) alpha carveol (3.4%), Alpha Terpeneol (4.3%), Geraniol (2%), Linolool (1.1%)	(15)
Lavras, MG Brazil (<i>C. viminalis</i>) leaf	1,8-cineole (84.6%), alpha pinene (10.28%), alpha terpeneol (2.59%)	(16)
Lavras, MG Brazil (<i>C. viminalis</i>) flowers	1,8-cineole (61.47%), alpha pinene (21.48%), alpha terpeneol (2.79%)	(16)
Alexandria Egypt (<i>Callistemon viminalis</i>) leaf	1,8-cineole (64.53%), alpha pinene (9.69%), alpha terpeneol (7.9%), Pinocarvone (3.45%), Terpinen-4-ol (2.86%), Carvone (1.5%), Methyl acetate (2.21%), Caryophyllene oxide (1.57%), Spathulenol (1.23%)	(17)
Thrissur Kerala India <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> leaf	1,8-cineole (19.17%), alpha pinene (10.28%), alpha terpeneol (11.51%), alpha-Phellandrene (9.55%), Terpinen-4-ol (3.89%),	(2)
Eastern Cape Province of South Africa (Seed oil <i>Callistemon citrinus</i>)	1,8-cineole (37.56%) alpha pinene (13.2%) Camphene (4.36%) alpha phellendrene (5.15%) Terpinen-4-ol (5.99%) alpha terpeneol (8.11%)	(18)
Madras India <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> leaf	1,8-cineole (40.44%) Linolool (27.34%) alpha Pinene (17.46%)	(19)
Mansoura University, Egypt <i>Callistemon viminalis</i> leaf	1,8-cineole (66.36%) alpha Pinene (20.43%) α -terpineol (6.65%)	(20)
Lucknow Uttar Pradesh <i>Callistemon viminalis</i> , Leaf	1,8-cineole (61.7%) alpha Pinene (24.2%) menthyl acetate (5.3%)	(21)
Giza, Egypt <i>Callistemon citrinus</i> leaf	1,8-cineole (70.77%) alpha Pinene (2.09%) α -terpineol (4.27%) Linolool (13.8%)	(1)

DISCUSSION

The GC-MS analysis of *Callistemon citrinus* leaf oil from Roorkee, Haridwar (Uttarakhand, North India) reveals a diverse array of volatile compounds typical of the *Callistemon* genus, including monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, and oxygenated derivatives. Key compounds identified include 1,8-Cineol, α -terpinol, α -pinene, β -pinene, P-Cymene, and limonene, which contribute to the oil's aromatic, medicinal, and potential bioactive properties.^[22]

Monoterpenes like α -pinene, β -pinene, and P-Cymene are known for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, enhancing the therapeutic potential of the oil. α -Pinene, in particular, has bronchodilator effects and antimicrobial properties. Sesquiterpenes, including caryophyllene oxide and spathulenol, offer anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antimicrobial, and antifungal benefits. The oil also contains oxygenated compounds like 1,8-cineole and linalool, which contribute to the oil's pleasant aroma and therapeutic effects, including anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and expectorant properties.^[23,24]

Uncommon compounds such as 5-methyl-5-nitro-2-(prop-1-en-1-yl)-1,3-dioxane and leptospermone offer potential unique biological activities, though further study is needed.^[25] Eugenol and geraniol, known for their pharmacological properties, also feature prominently in the oil.^[26]

Novelty and Implications of Findings

Although cineole-dominant chemotypes are common in *Callistemon citrinus*, the Roorkee oil exhibited an unusually high proportion of 1,8-cineole, ranking among the highest reported globally. This outcome broadens the current understanding of chemotypic diversity within the species and underscores its potential value in medicinal, aromatherapeutic, and industrial sectors, particularly in formulations targeting respiratory health where 1,8-cineole is a principal active compound. Furthermore, the comparative analysis emphasizes the role of chemotype selection in achieving consistent bioactivity and supports the development of robust quality standards for therapeutic and commercial applications.^[27,28]

Regional Differences in Essential Oil Composition of *Callistemon* Species: A Comparative Overview

The essential oils obtained from various *Callistemon* species—including *C. citrinus*, *C. viminalis*, and *C. comboynensis*—show significant chemical variation influenced by both geographic region and the specific plant part used for extraction. In South Africa, this variation is especially noticeable. Oils extracted from the fruit are rich in sesquiterpenes like α -eudesmol (12.93%) and caryophyllene (11.89%), along with minor contributions from bornyl acetate and 1,8-cineole. Meanwhile, the leaf oil exhibits a strong 1,8-cineole profile (48.98%) accompanied by α -pinene (20.02%). The seed oil maintains a similar pattern but with even higher levels of 1,8-cineole (56%) and α -pinene (31.03%), indicating that seeds and leaves share a stable 1,8-cineole- α -pinene chemotype, while fruits lean towards sesquiterpene dominance.^[7]

In the Himalayan region of India, essential oil composition shows clear regional and altitudinal influences. Oils from the fruit typically contain 1,8-cineole (36.6%) and α -pinene (29.7%). Leaf oils, especially from mid-altitude regions, are richer in α -pinene (32.3%) with notable amounts of α -terpineol (14.6%) and limonene (13.1%). However, in the lower Himalayas, leaf oils shift to a composition dominated by 1,8-cineole (66.3%) and a reduced level of α -pinene (18.7%), further emphasizing the impact of elevation on oil constituents.^[3]

Studies from Iran also reflect a certain degree of variation but point to a broadly similar trend. Leaf oils show a fluctuating 1,8-cineole range from 34.2% to 67.6%, with α -pinene appearing consistently as a secondary component. The oil derived from fruits typically contains α -pinene (25.7%) and lower amounts of 1,8-cineole (18.1%), while the stem oil includes 1,8-cineole (41.3%), α -pinene (19.1%), and α -terpineol (4.1%). These values suggest a chemotype generally dominated by 1,8-cineole and α -pinene, occasionally accompanied by terpineol.^[29,10]

On Reunion Island, the oil from *Callistemon citrinus* leaves demonstrates a classic cineol-rich chemotype, with 1,8-cineole accounting for 68% of the composition, followed by α -pinene (12.8%) and α -terpineol (10.6%).^[11] In Pakistan, although limited data is available, the presence of both 1,8-cineole and α -terpineol aligns with mixed monoterpenoid chemotypes seen in other regions.^[13]

From Roorkee in Uttarakhand, India, *C. lanceolatus* leaf oil stands out with one of the highest reported concentrations of 1,8-cineole (75.4%), alongside α -terpineol (7.95%), d-limonene (5.65%), and α -pinene (3.74%), representing a particularly cineol-rich profile.

The chemical profiles of Egyptian *Callistemon* species present a more diverse picture. For *C. comboynensis*, the essential oil contains 1,8-cineol (53.3%), eugenol (12.1%), methyleugenol (9.2%), and α -pinene (8.3%).^[15] *C. viminalis* from Egypt is dominated by cineol (64.53%) with a secondary α -pinene content (9.69%).^[17] Meanwhile, *C. citrinus* shows a more balanced profile, including 1,8-cineol (70.77%), linalool (13.8%), α -pinene (2.09%), and β -pinene (1.42%).^[1]

In Brazil, *C. viminalis* oil is again characterized by high levels of 1,8-cineol (84.6%) and α -pinene (10.28%), showing strong similarity to the South Africa variant.^[16, 12] In Kerala (India), the *C. citrinus* oil has a more complex mix with moderate 1,8-cineol (19.17%),

increased α -terpineol (11.51%), and α -phellandrene (9.55%)². In Madras (Chennai), the *C. citrinus* profile includes 1,8-cineol (40.44%), linalool (27.34%), and α -pinene (17.46%), which closely matches the South Africa *C. citrinus* pattern.^[19]

This comparative study helps categorize the chemotypes into clear groups: cineol-dominant chemotypes are found in Brazil, Reunion, Roorkee, and some Iranian and Egyptian samples; mixed cineol- α -pinene-terpineol chemotypes are typical of South Africa, Kerala, and Pakistan; cineol-linalool-rich profiles are common in Madras and Egyptian *C. citrinus*; and sesquiterpene-rich types are mainly observed in South African fruit oils. These findings highlight how environmental and geographical conditions, along with plant part selection, significantly affect the essential oil composition in *Callistemon* species. Understanding this variability is vital for effectively utilizing these oils in pharmaceutical and industrial applications.

Limitations of the Study

This study was carried out using a single batch of *Callistemon citrinus* leaves, as restrictions on analytical resources prevented replicate GC-MS runs ($n \geq 3$). Consequently, the oil yield and composition presented here reflect one batch only, and no statistical comparisons between multiple replicates were possible. Quantification was performed through GC-MS area normalization rather than GC-FID, which may result in minor deviations from true absolute concentrations. We recognize this as a methodological constraint and plan to incorporate GC-FID validation in future investigations. Furthermore, a few trace constituents with similarity scores below 90% were identified solely through library matching and are reported as tentative. Expanded multi-seasonal and multi-location sampling, together with replicated analyses, will be necessary to fully understand chemotypic diversity and the environmental factors shaping it.

CONCLUSION

The GC-MS analysis of *Callistemon lanceolatus* leaf oil from Roorkee, Uttarakhand, reveals a cineol-rich chemotype with a significant presence of bioactive compounds such as 1,8-cineol, α -terpineol, d-limonene, and α -pinene. These constituents contribute to the oil's therapeutic potential, particularly in antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant applications. Comparative regional analysis demonstrates considerable chemical diversity among *Callistemon* species, influenced by geographic location, plant part, and environmental factors. While cineol remains a dominant component across most samples, the relative

abundance of α -pinene, terpineols, linalool, and sesquiterpenes creates distinct chemotypes—ranging from cineol-dominant to mixed and sesquiterpene-rich profiles. The sample from Roorkee stands out for its exceptionally high 1, 8 cineole content, aligning it with other cineol-rich profiles from regions like Brazil and Reunion Island. These findings not only highlight the phytochemical richness of *Callistemon lanceolatus* but also emphasize the importance of regional profiling for targeted pharmacological and industrial utilization of essential oils.

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